

SKILL AND SELF-RELIANT INDIA

K.C. Mahadesha

Academician, Syndicate Member, Mangalore University

‘Skill India mission is not merely to fill pockets but to bring a sense of self-confidence among the poor’

- Prime Minister Modi

ABSTRACT:

Skill development and Self-Reliant India go hand in hand. Nothing can prevent the country in accomplishing its goal or hampers the growth of the economic growth of the country where the people are smart, efficient, skilled and talented. In fact, Japan achieved a lot and emerged as one of the developed countries despite the dearth of the resources because of talented, skilled and self-Reliant people. The measures taken by the government to strengthen the people through Skill and Self-Reliant India mission. The initiatives and schemes undertaken in last few years have already paved the way for this journey towards making India Self-Reliant. A self-reliant economy has to mean self-reliant for each and every member of our population. So, the most important objectives of a development strategy that forces on self-reliance is inclusive growth. So that the success of any nation shall be determined through self-reliant citizens for self-reliant India.

Key words: Skill, Self-Reliant, Mission, growth, development, PMKVY, Knowledge, Livelihood, SANKALP.

INTRODUCTION:

The wealth of nations stems from the drive and creativity of its people. A self-reliant India will be built by self-reliant citizens. India is a family of 130 crore Indians. If each one of the family members gainfully contributes to the economy and there by Rastra Nirman, then our population becomes our collective strength and not a weakness. Citizens that Energetically contribute with confidence in their own capability will be able to move mountains

A person becomes independent if he/she has skills and can earn their own livelihood. Government needs to facilitate this by providing opportunities for skilling. For Indian to be self-reliant, the social compact between the Government and citizens has, in essence, to be one where government actively supports personal responsibility, rather than government support substituting personal responsibilities or community responsibility. Active government support for self-reliant citizens requires our citizens to retain their personal drive and dignity as part of this compact. Therefore, subsidies, especially those that go to the relatively well-off, cannot be consistent with a self-reliant India.

Science and Technology has played a critical role in the development of the nation. For the rural populace. In particular, it has been far more impactful. Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyaan assured Agri produce price and quality assurance. Facilitative larger frame work will be created to enable farmers for engaging with processors, aggregators, large retailers, exporters etc., in a fair and transparent manner. Risk mitigation for farmers, assured returns and quality standardization shall form integral part of the frame work.

Skill India Mission is one of the flag ship programmes of Narendra Modi Government is a comprehensive program launched in 2015. Mr. Narendra Modi in accordance with the World Youth

Skills Day declared for the first time on 15th July, 2015. The scheme was launched with the vision of making India self-reliant.

India comes across as a young nation with nearly 65 percent of its population falling under the 35 making it largely a young nation. The term Youth as defined by the UNESCO as a period of transition from the dependence on childhood to adulthood's independence and awareness of our independence as members of a community. Youth is more fluid category than a fixed age group often identified by their zeal and enthusiasm to bring rapid transformation. The initiative aimed to develop industrial and entrepreneurial skills among Indians through training programmes, bridging the gap between the industry demands and the skill requirements. This is a major initiative involving all segments of society and this is India's first integrated national scheme for developing skills and promoting entrepreneurship on a larger scale. Skill India initiative is considered to be the world's largest initiative to train the workforce in a single geographical location.

India's 54% of the population is below 25 years of age. With a high working-age population, the development of skilled and educated manpower will play a major role in enhancing the country's economy. More than 50% of the population depends on agriculture for livelihood, though the returns are very minimal. Therefore, the younger generation is shifting towards the secondary and tertiary sectors for employment. Hence, the need to improve the skills of youth to make them employable in these sectors arises.

The Skill India Mission, the government aims to develop practical skills, required by the industry to improve the employment rate. According to the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE), the unemployment rate fell to 6.5% in January 2021 from 9.1% in December 2020, whereas the employment rate rose to 37.9% in January 2021 from 36.9% in December 2020.

Skill India campaign was launched on 15 July 2015 by prime Minister. The campaign aims to impart training to 400 million (40 crore) people in India in different skills by 2022 so that they can achieve employment. Under this campaign various initiative is taken by government like National Skill Development Mission,

National Policy for Skill Development and Entrepreneurship, 2015, Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojna (PMKVY) and Skill Loan Scheme. The program aims to skill the youths in such a way so that they get employment and improve entrepreneurship qualities.

It includes training, support and guidance for all occupations that were of traditional type like carpenters, cobblers, welders, blacksmiths, masons, nurses, tailors, weavers etc. Under this campaign more emphasis will be given to new areas like real estate, construction, transportation, textile, gem industry, jewelry designing, banking, tourism and various other sectors, where skill development is inadequate or nil.

Another remarkable features of the Skill India programme would be to create a hallmark called "Rural India Skill", so as to standardize and certify the training process. Tailor-made, need-based programmes would be initiated for specific age groups which can be like language and communication skills, life and positive thinking skills, personality development skills, management skills, behavioural skills, including job and employability skill.

The main idea behind skill India is to raise confidence, improve productivity and give direction through proper skill development. Skill India will provide blue-collar jobs to the youths. This paper tries to examine the Prospects of skill India campaign and its advantage.

Significance of the study:

The success of any country shall be determined through people's participation in economic growth and development of the country. Many leaders alarming at the higher level and it is echoing that population growth affects and hampers the economic growth of the country. Of course, it can't be denied and refused, however skilled population is the crux of the nation's growth. It is imperative to inculcate and promote such skill in youths and thereby strengthen the economic democracy of the country. In this regard efforts are made by the government of India under the dynamic leadership of Narendra Modi and dedicated civil servants.

Skills and knowledge are the forces that shape the country's development. They play a critical role in the country's economy and social development. As India advances closer to becoming a knowledge-based economy, it becomes more critical for the country to enhance its skills base. To achieve the twin goals of inclusive development and economic growth, India's gross domestic product needs to grow at an annual rate of 8% to 9%. This requires a balanced and resilient growth strategy supported by a skilled workforce. Considering the need for skill development programs in the country, National Skill Development Policy was started in 2009.

"Skill is the ability to complete a particular task efficiently and effectively". If a worker lacks specific skills, they will be unable to do the job to the specified specifications. Lack of skills leads to low productivity, wastage of raw materials, and low quality of products at the workplace. Therefore, skills development is very important to improve the industry's performance. The development of skills refers to the capacity that individuals have acquired through various levels of education and training, which enables them to become highly productive in the economy.

According to the 12th Five Year Plan, skill development initiatives of 2009 were mostly operated by the government, with little link to market demand. It has recommended for the creation of an enabling framework to encourage private investment in vocational training through Public-Private Partnerships. In 2009, the National Skill Development Policy was created in response to the critical demand for skill development. Given the country's massive paradigm change in the skilling and entrepreneurial environment and the experience obtained through the implementation of numerous skill development programs, a review of the existing policy is urgently required. Furthermore, the 2009 Policy calls for a review every five years to keep the policy framework up to date with changing national and worldwide trends. Therefore, in July 2014, the Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports established a department of skill development and entrepreneurship, which was then promoted to a full-fledged ministry in November 2014. The ministry's responsibilities include coordinating and evolving skill development frameworks, mapping existing skills and certification, and establishing industry- institute links, among other things. 2015, "National Policy for Skill Development and Entrepreneurship" replaced the 2009 policy. Its goal is to offer a unified framework for all skilling operations in the country, aligning them to common criteria and connecting skilling to demand centers. The fundamental goal of this approach is to address the difficulty of skilling at scale while maintaining speed, consistency, and long-term viability. The policy identifies the general institutional framework that will operate as a vehicle to achieve the desired outcomes in addition to spelling out the aims and expected outcomes.

Scope of the study: The scope of the study has been widened with the introduction of many pro people programmes. Indeed, it is very essential to enhance the skill of the people especially the youths whose talents and skill need to be extracted for the wellbeing of the individual as

well as the nation. Workforce skill development is essential for several reasons:

Demand for Skilled Workers: There is a growing demand for a skilled workforce in India. The Confederation of Indian Industry (CII) estimates that by 2023, the country will require about 300 million skilled workers to meet the demands of various sectors, particularly manufacturing.

Rising Unemployment: The unemployment rate in India has been on the rise, reaching around 7% or 8% in 2022 compared to about 5% five years ago. The pandemic has worsened the situation, causing many people to leave the workforce due to job dissatisfaction and lockdowns.

Supply and Demand Imbalance: India faces a problem of not enough job opportunities being created while professionals entering the job market lack the necessary skills. This has led to increasing unemployment rates and low employability.

The program aims to skill the youths in such a way so that they get employment and improve entrepreneurship qualities. The main idea behind skill India is to raise confidence, improve productivity and give direction through proper skill development. Skill India will provide blue-collar jobs to the youths.

1. Bridging the gap between the industry demands and the individual skill requirements for employment generation.
2. Creating employment opportunities for the development of young talents.
3. Strengthening the Indian youth as a workforce for world markets.
4. Building up the competitiveness of Indian businesses.
5. Building up true marketplace capabilities rather than mere qualifications.
6. Diversifying the skill development program to meet the demands of a dynamic market.
7. Training people in areas like real estate, construction, transportation, textile, gem industry, banking and tourism where the skill development is inadequate.
8. Identifying and developing the new sectors that require skill enhancement. Check out the article on Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana.

The Government of India has launched various skill development schemes, including

- Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY)
- Skills Acquisition and Knowledge Awareness for Livelihood Promotion (**SANKALP**)
- UDAAN
- Standard Training Assessment and Reward Scheme (STAR)
- Polytechnic Schemes
- Vocationalisation of Education
- Rozgar Mela
- Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendra (PMKK)
- Capacity Building Scheme
- Udaan
- School Initiatives and Higher Education
- India International Skill Centers (IISCs)

- Pre-Departure Orientation Training (PDOT)

Features of the Skill India Mission

1. The initiative provides the younger generation with employment opportunities and also helps them launch their MSMEs.
2. It provides training as well as financial & technical assistance to new traders stepping into the market.
3. It lays emphasis on core sectors like construction, banking and finance, transportation, tourism and entrepreneurship.
4. Under the initiative, India has partnered with other countries and overseas educational institutions for providing training that is on par with the international standards.
5. It focuses on providing internationally acceptable training to people to improve their communication, entrepreneurial and management skills. Read about Pradhan Mantri Van Dhan Yojana here! Initiatives Under the Skill India Mission To attain the objectives of the Skill India initiative, the government has introduced many schemes, ensuring its implementation all across the country.

1. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY)

- The Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship (MSDE) implemented this scheme enabling the Indian youth to take up skill training linked to a specific industry. This would enable them to lead a better livelihood. The scheme provides monetary rewards for those who complete the training program.
- Skill councils like Agriculture Sector Skill Council, Food Industry Capacity and Skill Initiative (FICSI) that are sector-specific are established under PMKVY.

The components of the PMKVY are:

- a. Short-term training
- b. Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL)
- c. Kaushal and Rozgar Mela
- d. Placement Assistance
- e. Continuous Monitoring
- f. Standardized Branding and Communication

2. Pradhan Mantri YUVA Yojana (PM YUVA Yojana)

- This scheme focuses on creating an enabling environment through entrepreneurship education
- This scheme was launched with the intent of supporting the youth willing to take up training programs within the country.
- It replaced the earlier Indian Banks Association (IBA) Model Loan Scheme for

Vocational Education and Training.

- An Indian citizen taking admission to a course offered by the educational and training institutes recognized as a part of this scheme, can avail loans that part of the population that is underprivileged (scheduled castes/scheduled tribes/minorities), with minimum infrastructure and resources.

- Under the Jan Shiksha Sansthan, around 6.68 lakh candidates have been trained between FY19 and FY21 (until February 23, 2021).

3. Skills Acquisition and Knowledge Awareness for Livelihood Promotion (SANKALP Scheme)

- The SANKALP scheme launched in January 2018 is a program funded by the World Bank and is managed under the Ministry of Skill Development.
- The overall cost of this project stands at 675 million USD, including the 500 million USD assistance from the World Bank that is going to be implemented in two parts over six years, until March 2023. UDAAN
- The UDAAN scheme acts as a bridge between the corporate sector and the Home Ministry offering skill training to the youth of J&K.
- Graduates, Under-graduates and holders of Diploma are eligible to participate in this scheme.
- This scheme works with the objective of providing the best access of Corporate India to the unemployed.
- Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendra (PMKKs) Check out this article on Pradhan Mantri Kisan Sampada Yojana here! Effectiveness of the Skill India Mission
- According to the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CIME), the unemployment rate reached about 34% among the people aged 20-24 in the first quarter of 2019 which summed up to 37.9% of the urban lot.
- In 2017, only 5.5 million jobs were created with around 8 million job seekers entering the job market each year.
- According to the Periodic Labor Force Survey (PLFS) 2018, the unemployment rate among the urban population aged 15-29 years was 23.7%.
- According to a recent survey, 48% of employers reported difficulties in filling the vacancies due to the shortage of necessary skills.
- The CIME report has found that the more educated people are, the more likely they remain unemployed and the PLFS report of 2018 showed that 33% of those formally trained aged 15-29 years were unemployed.
- The government had expected the PMKVY trainees to set up their own enterprises. But, only 24% of the trainees started a business and of them, only 10,000 applied for loans under MUDRA.

4. Measures taken for farmers- Rs 30,000 crore Additional Emergency Working Capital for farmers through NABARD-over and above Rs. 90,000 crores NABARD is providing for crop loans to Rural Cooperative Banks and RRBs.

5. Mission of Indradhanush- Vaccination cover against 7 diseases to more than 89 lakh children by 2020 (Missies, Polio, pertussis, Tetanus, TB, Diphtheria, Hepatitis B)

- PMKVY is the flagship scheme of the Labour and Employment Ministry.
- The scheme among others, also imparts training in soft skills, entrepreneurship, financial and digital literacy.

3. The scheme aims to align the competencies of the unregulated workforce of the country with the National Skill Qualification Framework.

Key issues and challenges:

- ❑ **Lack of Awareness:** Many individuals, especially in rural areas, lack awareness about skill development programs and their benefits. They may not know about the available opportunities or how to access them.
- ❑ **Lack of Industry Linkages:** Limited collaboration between skill training institutions and industries leads to a gap between what is taught and what the job market demands.
- ❑ **Perception and Stigma:** There is a perception among some sections of society that vocational training is inferior to traditional education, leading to a stigma around pursuing skill development courses
- ❑ **Insufficient training capacity:** The training was not sufficient to ensure a job for those who got the training – and this is why the employability rate remains very low.
- ❑ **Lack of entrepreneurship skills:** While the government expected that some of the PMKVY-trainees would create their own enterprise, only 24% of the trainees started their business. And out of them, only 10,000 applied for MUDRA loans.
- ❑ **Low industry interface:** Most of the training institutes have low industry interface as a result of which the performance of the skill development sector is poor in terms of placement records and salaries offered.
- ❑ **Low student mobilization:** The enrolment in skill institutes like ITIs, and polytechnics, remains low as compared to their enrolment capacity. This is due to low awareness level among youths about the skill development programmes.
- ❑ **Employers' unwillingness:** India's joblessness issue is not only a skills problem; it is representative of the lack of appetite of industrialists and SMEs for recruiting. Due to limited access to credit because of Banks' NPAs, investment rate has declined and thus a negative impact on job creation.
- ❑ **Mobility and Accessibility:** Access to skill development programs can be a challenge for people living in remote or disadvantaged areas.
- ❑ **Funding and Sustainability:** Skill development programs require significant funding for infrastructure, training, and other resources. Ensuring sustainable funding is essential for the continuity and success of these initiatives.
- ❑ **Quality of Training:** The quality of skill training programs varies widely. Some programs may not meet industry standards, leading to graduates with inadequate skills and knowledge for the job market.
- ❑ **Relevance to Industry Needs:** Skill development programs may not always align with the current and future needs of industries. This mismatch between the skills taught and the skills required by employers can lead to underemployment or unemployment.
- ❑ **Infrastructure and Resources:** Inadequate infrastructure and resources can limit the effectiveness of skill development initiatives. Lack of modern equipment and facilities hampers practical training.

- **Trainer Quality:** The competence and training of instructors and trainers can impact the quality of skill training.

Promoting skilling in India requires a comprehensive and multi-pronged approach involving the government, private sector, educational institutions, and civil society.

Measures to promote skilling in India:

1. **Strengthening Vocational Education:** Enhance vocational education in schools and colleges by introducing skill-focused courses and practical training to instill job-ready skills from an early age.
2. **Industry Partnerships:** Foster strong collaborations between skill training institutions and industries to align training with the current and future needs of the job market.
3. **Focus on Emerging Technologies:** Include training programs for emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, data science, and renewable energy to meet the demands of the future job market.
4. **Support for Marginalized Groups:** Design targeted skill development initiatives for marginalized groups, including women, differently-abled individuals, and economically disadvantaged communities.
5. **Government Schemes:** Strengthen existing skill development schemes like the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) and introduce new schemes to cater to specific skill requirements.
6. **Skill Development Centers:** Establish and support skill development centers across the country to provide accessible training opportunities for different sectors.
7. **Trainer Training Programs:** Conduct regular training programs for instructors and trainers to improve their skills and ensure high-quality training delivery.
8. **Certification and Recognition:** Provide formal certification for skill development programs to increase their credibility and recognition among employers.
9. **Financial Incentives:** Offer financial incentives to individuals and businesses that invest in skill development, such as tax benefits and subsidies.
10. **Entrepreneurship Training:** Introduce entrepreneurship development programs to encourage individuals to start their own businesses and create jobs for others.
11. **Public-Private Partnerships:** Encourage public-private partnerships to combine resources and expertise for effective skill development initiatives.
12. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Establish a robust monitoring and evaluation system to measure the outcomes of skill development programs and make necessary improvements.

CONCLUSION:

Self-reliant is not doing everything yourself. Whether it is an individual or nation, self-India doesn't imply doing everything yourself. Similarly building a self-reliant economy does not mean building an economy in isolation. Self-reliance implies recognizing that when we depend on other for help, there will be times when such help will not be forthcoming. As the times we seek help may be the times when we are most vulnerable, self-reliance implies building the necessary capability to be independent at the most vulnerable times. Thus, self-reliance does not imply complacent self-

sufficiency, where India cuts its self-off from the rest of the world and thereby avoids competing with the best in the world and benchmarking itself against them. Instead, self-reliance requires delineating sectors that are strategically critical to the nation and investing in these sectors so that our dependence during vulnerable times is minimised. So, it is the obligation of every individual towards the state and involve in strengthening the ethical as well as economic base of the country which lends glory to our rich heritage. Skill development is the most important aspect for the development of the country. It needs a coordinated effort from all the agencies, stakeholders and the students to make it a successful program. India has a 'demographic dividend' and it has to work toward making it useful for the country. It will not only add value to the economy of the country but will be supporting the 'Make in India' campaign by providing the skilled workforce in the country. Like China, our vocational training programs should be included at the school level itself.

The Public Private Partnership plays a key and an important role in the development and enhancement of skills. NSDC has made some progress in improving the training infrastructure in the private sector by having more and more Public Private Partnership. There has been a growth in such partnership over a few years. Such partnerships are also being encouraged in rural areas which consist of a considerable high number of aspirants. It becomes extremely important to strengthen the tie-ups with the training institutes to ensure that the quality is maintained and the model is sustainable too. Since, there will be a huge demand in the Retail and the Hospitality Sector so the government needs to focus on the non-technical skills too. The Skilled India initiatives need to focus and develop more entrepreneurship skills amongst the workforce in order to ensure more job generation in the country. The Startup India and Stand-up India schemes need to be advertised well in the market in order to have more people taking advantage of such a model. The NSDC should also focus on the unorganized sector in order to make the Skill India campaign a successful model.

Today workforce skill development is necessary to bridge the gap between job opportunities and the skill sets of job seekers, reduce unemployment rates, and meet the increasing demand for skilled workers in India's evolving economy. Addressing these issues requires a multi-faceted approach involving government support, private-sector collaboration, increased awareness, improved training quality, and regular assessment of outcomes. By tackling these aforesaid challenges, India can enhance its skilling ecosystem and empower its workforce for a more prosperous future.

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